

MY PRESIDENT IS MY PRIDE

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Annotation: *Through this article, you will learn about the devotion of the younger generation to the motherland and the level of trust and pride in the head of state.*

Key words: *patriot, country, head of state, pride, responsibility.*

Since the formation of the new Uzbekistan, the state has been paying special attention to youth issues. He relied on the younger generation to consistently implement reforms in the field of education. The Decree of President Sh. is a great help [1]. The level of intellectual knowledge of young people plays a special role in the development of society. Intellectual potential is one of the most important factors that determine the development of all peoples, the whole state and society in all times, because it is based on such elements as science, spirituality, culture, nationality, history. Today, in the age of globalization and the information age, the question of how human thinking and intellectual potential develops, as well as whether the youth's intellect can withstand such violence, is a matter of urgency. European scientists such as A.G.Zdravomyslov, I.Tallman, P.Pindas have done a lot of research in assessing the place of the period. According to them, the socialization of young people is largely due to the development of science and technology. The multidisciplinary development of society has become the basis for determining the social status of young people. [2]

Also, in the process of studying this issue, the classic representatives of world sociology, political science, pedagogy and psychology D. Locke, G. Hegel, F. Engels, M. Weber, J. Sartre, K. Jaspers, E. Fromm, E. Durkheim, L. The views of Levi-Brule, A. Toynbee, O. Spengler, N. Berdyaev, A. Maslow, V. Frankl are of great importance.

At present, the tasks set in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 are being consistently implemented in our country. This policy document paved the way for our country to enter a completely new stage of development. The adoption of the Action Strategy is a big step for Uzbekistan, and the country has acted consistently and confidently in this regard, creating the necessary solid foundation.

The lives, dreams, goals and worldviews of great people, unlike others, are in harmony with the happiness, destiny and prosperity of their countrymen. They are selfless people.

The prudent policy pursued by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to ensure the well-being of the people on the basis of vital criteria is reflected in the life and daily life of our people, the social activity of our people and confidence in the future are growing. From the day my President was elected head of state, we have all witnessed the formation of a new Uzbekistan.

It also means an increase in the field of education aimed at the intellectual development and activity of the younger generation, as well as the formation and strengthening of love for the true homeland in the hearts of the talented generation. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2017 "On measures to further improve the activities of secondary special, vocational education institutions" [3] will inevitably bring the work in this direction to a new level. On measures to further develop the higher education system "[4]. The decision was made in order to radically improve the education system, to radically reconsider the meaning of training in accordance with the priorities of socio-economic development of the country, to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists at international standards. It should be noted that the head of our state, along with the younger generation, is constantly working hard for the well-being of our citizens.

In this regard, I quote the words of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "Living with human concerns is the highest criterion of humanity." "[5] My heart is filled with great pride and pride. All young people in Uzbekistan, like me, feel a great responsibility, along with great respect for the head of state. In response to the care shown to us, we promise to do our best to contribute to the development of our country.

Also, with the creation of the new Uzbekistan, the country has not only witnessed a period of development, but also increased its position as a leading state in Central Asia. Today, I can say that the President of Uzbekistan is recognized as a reformer in the international arena.

It should also be noted that in the early days of his presidency, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke of freedom of speech and the "loosening" of social networks, that is, one of the principles of democracy, free thinking. At the same time, since the launch of the President's Portal to listen to the people's concerns, social media has been flooded with calls, statements and letters asking for justice. There are thousands of examples of this.

Every time I read the historical literature of our ancestors, in our ancient country, along with national values and traditions, "Islam" is always focused on beliefs. In this regard, Uzbekistan is the most Muslim-majority country in the region. It is known that our country is one of the centers of Islamic culture. We do not have an official ban on religion. Thousands of mosques are at the service of our people. A great way was opened for religious ceremonies. The fact that all Muslims in our country are allowed to wear national and religious clothes on a voluntary basis means that the same policy of our President has set the path of the new Uzbekistan in a truly spiritual and enlightening way.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev told our young people that their great virtues, their actions as a Muslim, today increase our responsibility to protect our homeland, to be a loyal and worthy child of our leader.

As a student, I saw a great power in the image and biography of our President. From the first day he took office, he introduced the system of public receptions, expelled leaders and officials from the cool offices of the capital to the people in remote villages. I consider it a high human quality to prefer to be. This quality of kindness and generosity inherent in our people is not only supported in the highest political circles, but also seen by the head of state himself.

Also, one of the reforms of the President of Uzbekistan on education was the opening of a high-quality education system in all regions of the country, ie presidential schools. It is a radically new system today, in which all sciences are taught to perfection. As one of the results of these reforms, the opening of the Presidential School in Fergana at the initiative of our President is an example. Under the leadership of our teacher, who responds to the conditions created for us by the President and their policies, the students will be strengthened, and the efforts of our dedicated teachers will help us to grow our love for our country. Such opportunities given to us young people are a sign that important initiatives await each of us in the future.

It should be noted that the large-scale reforms being carried out in the education system of our country serve such noble purposes as educating a generation of young people who meet modern requirements, are independent, deep-thinking, fluent in foreign languages.

Today, New Uzbekistan is being built on the basis of the important idea of "a society with human dignity and a people's state." On the basis of this glorious goal set by the head of our state, our people are becoming a real author of new reforms. In this regard, the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, aimed at creating the necessary political, legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational basis for the reforms to

be implemented in the country over the next five years on the principle of "Strategy of Action - Towards Development Strategy." development strategy based on community feedback and suggestions. In particular, the Development Strategy and the "road map" for its implementation in 2022 envisage the achievement of more than a hundred goals and the implementation of various measures within the seven priorities of the country's development. [6] Now the main goal is for everyone to find their place in society, to benefit the people and their families. Another set of rules is "Man, society, state", and from this year onwards, the priority of human dignity is paramount.

In short, the social changes taking place in the life of the country are witnessing a new approach to the issue of the role of the younger generation in society. This approach is a key factor in the formation of initiative, aspiration, mobility in young people. Therefore, only if the harmoniously developed generation has a high level of spiritual maturity can they deeply understand the laws of development of social life, the essence of the rule of law and its only guarantee for humanity to live a just life.

Seeing such reforms and goals for the future, I came up with a compassionate term that is a sincere acknowledgment of my homeland. The prayers for the survival of our head of state and the peace of our country are an objective assessment of the state by the people, an unemocratic, simple and sincere wish. Indeed, for me, it is the saying, "My President is my pride!"

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